

Reproducibility Log 2

CroRIS → ROR matching (input for OpenAlex → DOI → Overton)

Purpose

The purpose of this step is to map Croatian public research institutions obtained from CroRIS (the authority list produced in Reproducibility Log 1) to **ROR identifiers**, which are required for the next stage: querying **OpenAlex** by ROR ID to retrieve affiliated works and extract **DOIs**, and then using those DOIs as inputs for **Overton**.

Input: the CroRIS-derived authority list of Croatian public research institutions (HR/EN names + institution type + MZO identifier) created in Log 1.¹

Log 1 defines this table explicitly as an “authority list” used to standardize organization names.

Data sources

- **CroRIS API:** registry of research institutions. We restrict to public ownership and to institution types relevant for this study, following the filtering logic used in Log 1.
- **ROR API:** ROR registry entries for Croatia (`country_code:HR`), including names, types, and status fields.

Implementation (R)

The workflow is implemented in R and consists of two retrieval steps and one matching step:

1. Retrieve and filter CroRIS institutions

We use the CroRIS endpoint for scientific institutions and filter to:

- `tipVlasnistva == "public"` (public ownership), and
- institution types: *university*, *faculty*, *public research institute* (Croatian labels: “sveučilište”, “fakultet”, “javni znanstveni institut”).

This is consistent with the approach documented in Log 1.

2. Retrieve ROR institutions for Croatia and clean the candidate set

We page through the ROR API query `filter=country.country_code:HR`, then keep only:

- organizations with `status == "active"`, and
- organizations whose `types` include relevant categories (e.g., *education*, *facility*).

For each ROR record we extract:

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/17912452>

- the full ROR identifier and a shortened ROR ID (suffix),
 - a preferred display name (prioritizing entries tagged as `ror_display` where available).
3. **Match CroRIS institutions to ROR records**
- For each CroRIS institution, we compute string similarity between:
- CroRIS HR name vs ROR display name, and
 - CroRIS EN name vs ROR display name,
- and retain the best-scoring candidate. The similarity metric used is **Jaccard similarity over character trigrams**.
4. Decision logic:
- **Direct match**: if best similarity score ≥ 0.50 , assign that ROR ID.
 - **Faculties**: if no strong direct match, assign the ROR ID of the corresponding **parent university** (using a manually verified city→university mapping for major Croatian universities), or flag for manual resolution if the parent cannot be inferred.
 - **Universities**: assign via the same city-based mapping where applicable, otherwise flag for manual lookup.
 - **Public research institutes**: if best score ≥ 0.35 , assign as “verify match”; otherwise flag for manual lookup.

Outputs

- [crosis_ror_matching_results.xlsx](#)
Full matching output including: CroRIS HR/EN names, institution type, suggested ROR ID, best candidate ROR ID and name, match score, and a note describing the decision path (e.g., “Direct match”, “Verify match”, “Faculty → parent university”, “manual lookup”).
- [crosis_institutions_with_ror.xlsx](#)
A cleaned subset containing only institutions with an assigned ROR ID, intended as the direct input for the next step (OpenAlex query by ROR).

Manual review and auditability

Because organization-name matching is sensitive to naming variants and incomplete/heterogeneous affiliation strings (as already noted in Log 1 in the Overton affiliation context), we explicitly separate cases requiring manual verification and completion:

- institutions with no `Suggested_ROR` are exported for manual assignment via ROR search,
- borderline matches (“Verify match”) are retained but flagged for manual checking.

Code:

```
library(httr)
library(jsonlite)
library(tidyverse)
library(readxl)
library(writexl)

setwd("C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data")

cat("Step 1: Fetching CroRIS institutions...\n")

base_url <- "https://www.croris.hr/ustanove-api"
url <- paste0(base_url, "/upisnik-ustanova/ustanova/znanstvena")

res <- GET(url, accept("application/hal+json"))
stop_for_status(res)
txt <- content(res, as = "text", encoding = "UTF-8")
dat <- fromJSON(txt)

ustanove <- dat[["_embedded"]][["ustanove"]]

ustanove <- subset(
  ustanove,
  !is.na(tipVlasnistva) & tolower(tipVlasnistva) == "public"
)

vrsta_vec <- ustanove$vrstaUstanove$naziv
wanted_vrste <- c("sveučilište", "javni znanstveni institut", "fakultet")
mask_vrsta <- !is.na(vrsta_vec) & vrsta_vec %in% wanted_vrste
ustanove <- ustanove[mask_vrsta, ]

cat(" CroRIS institutions after filtering:", nrow(ustanove), "\n")

df_croris <- data.frame(
  naziv_hr = ustanove$puniNaziv,
  naziv_en = ifelse(!is.na(ustanove$puniNazivEn), ustanove$puniNazivEn, ustanove$nazivEn),
```

```

vrsta_ustanove = vrsta_vec[mask_vrsta],
stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)

cat("\nStep 2: Fetching ROR Croatian institutions...\n")

all_institutions <- list()
page <- 1

repeat {
  url <- paste0("https://api.ror.org/organizations?filter=country.country_code:HR&page=", page)

  res <- GET(url)
  stop_for_status(res)

  data <- fromJSON(content(res, as = "text", encoding = "UTF-8"))

  if (length(data$items) == 0) break

  all_institutions[[page]] <- data$items

  if (nrow(data$items) < 20) break

  page <- page + 1
  Sys.sleep(0.5)
}

df_ror_raw <- bind_rows(all_institutions)

cat(" Total Croatian institutions in ROR:", nrow(df_ror_raw), "\n")

df_ror <- df_ror_raw %>%
  filter(
    sapply(types, function(x) any(c("education", "facility") %in% x)),
    status == "active"
  )

df_ror$ror_id <- df_ror$id
df_ror$ror_id_short <- str_extract(df_ror$id, "[^/]+$")

df_ror$ror_name <- sapply(1:nrow(df_ror), function(i) {
  names_data <- df_ror$names[[i]]
  if (is.data.frame(names_data)) {

```

```

for (j in 1:nrow(names_data)) {
  if ("ror_display" %in% names_data$types[[j]]) {
    return(names_data$value[j])
  }
}
return(names_data$value[1])
}
return(NA)
})

df_ror_clean <- df_ror %>%
  select(ror_id, ror_id_short, ror_name) %>%
  distinct(ror_id_short, .keep_all = TRUE)

cat(" ROR institutions after filtering:", nrow(df_ror_clean), "\n")

parent_unis <- list(
  "Zagreb" = "00mv6sv71",
  "Split" = "00r9vb833",
  "Rijeka" = "058xyz380",
  "Osijek" = "02k7v4a75",
  "Dubrovnik" = "02bj7hv10",
  "Zadar" = "046z0he37",
  "Pula" = "006ks2460"
)

normalize_name <- function(x) {
  if (is.na(x)) return("")
  x %>%
  tolower() %>%
  str_replace_all("\\s+", " ") %>%
  str_trim()
}

jaccard_similarity <- function(a, b) {
  a_norm <- normalize_name(a)
  b_norm <- normalize_name(b)

  if (a_norm == "" || b_norm == "") return(0)

  get_trigrams <- function(s) {

```

```

    if (nchar(s) < 3) return(s)
    sapply(1:(nchar(s)-2), function(i) substr(s, i, i+2))
  }

a_tri <- get_trigrams(a_norm)
b_tri <- get_trigrams(b_norm)

intersection <- length(intersect(a_tri, b_tri))
union <- length(union(a_tri, b_tri))

if (union == 0) return(0)
return(intersection / union)
}

cat("\nStep 3: Matching CroRIS to ROR...\n")

results <- data.frame()

for (i in 1:nrow(df_croris)) {

  croris_hr <- df_croris$naziv_hr[i]
  croris_en <- df_croris$naziv_en[i]
  vrsta <- df_croris$vrsta_ustanove[i]

  best_score <- 0
  best_ror <- NA
  best_ror_name <- NA

  for (j in 1:nrow(df_ror_clean)) {
    ror_name <- df_ror_clean$ror_name[j]

    score_en <- jaccard_similarity(croris_en, ror_name)
    score_hr <- jaccard_similarity(croris_hr, ror_name)
    score <- max(score_en, score_hr)

    if (score > best_score) {
      best_score <- score
      best_ror <- df_ror_clean$ror_id_short[j]
      best_ror_name <- ror_name
    }
  }
}

```

```

suggested_ror <- NA
suggestion_note <- ""

if (best_score >= 0.5) {
  suggested_ror <- best_ror
  suggestion_note <- "Direct match"
}

else if (vrsta == "fakultet") {
  for (city in names(parent_unis)) {
    if (grepl(tolower(city), tolower(croris_hr)) ||
        grepl(tolower(city), tolower(croris_en))) {
      suggested_ror <- parent_unis[[city]]
      suggestion_note <- paste0("Faculty → parent university (", city, ")")
      break
    }
  }
  if (is.na(suggested_ror)) {
    suggestion_note <- "Faculty - find parent university manually"
  }
}

else if (vrsta == "sveučilište") {
  for (city in names(parent_unis)) {
    if (grepl(tolower(city), tolower(croris_hr))) {
      suggested_ror <- parent_unis[[city]]
      suggestion_note <- paste0("University - ", city)
      break
    }
  }
  if (is.na(suggested_ror)) {
    suggestion_note <- "University - find ROR manually"
  }
}

else if (vrsta == "javni znanstveni institut") {
  if (best_score >= 0.35) {
    suggested_ror <- best_ror
    suggestion_note <- paste0("Verify match (score=", round(best_score, 2), ")")
  } else {
    suggestion_note <- "Institute - find ROR manually"
  }
}

```

```

results <- rbind(results, data.frame(
  Naziv_HR = croris_hr,
  Naziv_EN = croris_en,
  Vrsta_ustanove = vrsta,
  Suggested_ROR = suggested_ror,
  ROR_note = suggestion_note,
  Best_ROR_match = ifelse(best_score >= 0.3, best_ror, NA),
  Best_ROR_name = ifelse(best_score >= 0.3, best_ror_name, NA),
  Match_score = round(best_score, 2),
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
))
}

cat("\n=====\n")
cat("MATCHING SUMMARY\n")
cat("=====\n")
cat("Total institutions:", nrow(results), "\n")
cat("With suggested ROR:", sum(!is.na(results$Suggested_ROR)), "\n")
cat("Need manual lookup:", sum(is.na(results$Suggested_ROR)), "\n")

cat("\nBy institution type:\n")
results %>%
  group_by(Vrsta_ustanove) %>%
  summarise(
    total = n(),
    with_ror = sum(!is.na(Suggested_ROR)),
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  print()

cat("\nInstitutions needing manual ROR lookup:\n")
results %>%
  filter(is.na(Suggested_ROR)) %>%
  select(Naziv_EN, Vrsta_ustanove) %>%
  print()

write_xlsx(results, "croris_ror_matching_results.xlsx")
cat("\nSaved: croris_ror_matching_results.xlsx\n")

results_for_openalex <- results %>%
  filter(!is.na(Suggested_ROR)) %>%
  select(Naziv_HR, Naziv_EN, Vrsta_ustanove, ROR_ID = Suggested_ROR)

```

```
write_xlsx(results_for_openalex, "roris_institutions_with_ror.xlsx")
cat("Saved: roris_institutions_with_ror.xlsx (", nrow(results_for_openalex), " institutions)\n")

cat("\n=====\n")
cat("NEXT STEP: Manually add ROR IDs for missing institutions\n")
cat("Search at: https://ror.org/search\n")
cat("=====\n")
```

2. Manual ROR assignment

During validation, we observed a substantial number of incorrect automated matches: even among the 31 cases flagged as “Direct match” by the similarity threshold, several were false positives.

Therefore, we switched to manual ROR assignment. Specifically, we populated the `croris_research_institutes_public` table by manually searching each institution in the ROR registry using the CroRIS-provided name fields (Croatian/English), because the CroRIS API does not provide an export field for ROR identifiers. It is saved in `croris_institutions_with_ror`.

3. Retrieve OpenAlex works by institution ROR and prepare DOI outputs

Goal: For each institution ROR (from `croris_research_institutes_public_ror.xlsx`), retrieve all OpenAlex works that are affiliated with that institution (via at least one authorship), extract their DOIs, and produce outputs that (a) preserve the DOI↔ROR linkage and (b) enable a global unique DOI list for downstream Overton querying.

Key points / logic:

- In OpenAlex, affiliation is represented through `authorships` → `institutions`.
- Querying the Works endpoint with the filter `institutions.ror:https://ror.org/<ROR>` returns works where **at least one author** is affiliated with the institution identified by that ROR.
- The filter `has_doi:true` is applied so only works with an available DOI are collected.
- Results are retrieved with **cursor pagination** (`cursor=*` and then `meta$next_cursor`) to exhaust all pages for each ROR.
- The pipeline intentionally keeps a **RAW per-ROR dataset** (`works_by_ror_RAW`) without any global deduplication to ensure that:
 - no DOI is dropped from a ROR just because the same DOI also appears under another ROR (multi-affiliation / multi-institution cases are preserved).

- Additional derived tables are produced for convenience:
 - `works_by_ror_dedup_work`: within-ROR deduplication by OpenAlex work ID (`openalex_id`).
 - `works_by_ror_dedup_doi`: within-ROR deduplication by DOI (`ror_short + doi`).
 - `doi_unique`: a **global unique DOI list** across all RORs for Overton querying.
 - `counts_by_ror`: DOI counts per ROR, computed from `works_by_ror_dedup_doi`.

Outputs:

- `openalex_works_by_ror_RAW.csv` — all retrieved works with DOI in long format (one row per work per ROR), no global deduplication.
- `openalex_doi_list_unique.csv` — global unique DOI list for Overton search.
- `openalex_dois_by_ror.xlsx` — workbook containing:
 - summary sheets: `works_by_ror_RAW`, `works_by_ror_dedup_work`, `works_by_ror_dedup_doi`, `doi_unique`, `counts_by_ror`
 - per-ROR sheets built from `works_by_ror_RAW`.
- For very large ROR result sets, per-ROR sheets are split into multiple worksheets if they exceed **25,000 rows**, named `<ROR>_01`, `<ROR>_02`, ... to keep sheets manageable and stable.

Code:

```
library(httr)
```

```
library(jsonlite)
```

```
library(readxl)
```

```
library(dplyr)
```

```
library(stringr)
```

```
library(purrr)
```

```
library(readr)
```

```
library(writexl)
```

```
library(tibble)
```

```
base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
in_path <- file.path(base_dir, "crois_research_institutes_public_ror.xlsx")

inst <- read_xlsx(in_path)

inst <- inst %>%
  mutate(ror_raw = str_to_lower(str_trim(as.character(ROR))))

inst_valid <- inst %>%
  mutate(is_ror_id = str_detect(ror_raw, "^[0-9a-z]{9}$")) %>%
  filter(is_ror_id) %>%
  distinct(ror_raw, .keep_all = TRUE)

ror_list <- sort(unique(inst_valid$ror_raw))
cat("Valid ROR IDs:", length(ror_list), "\n")

fetch_openalex_dois <- function(ror_short, per_page = 200) {

  cursor <- "*"
  out <- list()
  page_i <- 1

  repeat {
```

```
filter_str <- paste0(
  "institutions.ror:https://ror.org/", ror_short,
  ",has_doi:true"
)

url <- modify_url(
  "https://api.openalex.org/works",
  query = list(
    filter = filter_str,
    per_page = per_page,
    cursor = cursor,
    select = "id,doi,publication_year"
  )
)

res <- GET(
  url,
  user_agent("CroRIS-ROR-OpenAlex DOI harvesting (contact: mhoic@irmo.hr)")
)

stop_for_status(res)

dat <- fromJSON(content(res, as = "text", encoding = "UTF-8"), flatten = TRUE)

if (is.null(dat$results) || length(dat$results) == 0) break
```

```
df <- as_tibble(dat$results) %>%
  transmute(
    ror_short = ror_short,
    ror_url = paste0("https://ror.org/", ror_short),
    openalex_id = id,
    doi = doi,
    publication_year = publication_year
  )

out[[page_i]] <- df
page_i <- page_i + 1

next_cursor <- dat$meta$next_cursor
if (is.null(next_cursor) || next_cursor == "") break

cursor <- next_cursor
Sys.sleep(0.2) # be polite
}

bind_rows(out)
}

safe_fetch <- possibly(
```

```
fetch_openalex_dois,
otherwise = tibble(
  ror_short = character(),
  ror_url = character(),
  openalex_id = character(),
  doi = character(),
  publication_year = integer()
)
)

works_by_ror <- map_dfr(ror_list, ~ safe_fetch(.x, per_page = 200))

works_by_ror_RAW <- works_by_ror %>%
  filter(!is.na(doi), doi != "") %>%
  arrange(ror_short, publication_year, doi)

works_by_ror_dedup_work <- works_by_ror_RAW %>%
  distinct(ror_short, openalex_id, .keep_all = TRUE)

works_by_ror_dedup_doi <- works_by_ror_RAW %>%
  distinct(ror_short, doi, .keep_all = TRUE)

doi_unique <- works_by_ror_RAW %>%
  distinct(doi) %>%
```

```
arrange(doi)
```

```
counts_by_ror <- works_by_ror_dedup_doi %>%
```

```
  group_by(ror_short) %>%
```

```
  summarise(
```

```
    n_dois = n_distinct(doi),
```

```
    .groups = "drop"
```

```
  ) %>%
```

```
  arrange(desc(n_dois))
```

```
max_rows_per_sheet <- 25000
```

```
build_sheet_list <- function(df_one_ror, ror_short, max_rows = 25000) {
```

```
  df_one_ror <- df_one_ror %>% select(-ror_short) # optional
```

```
  n <- nrow(df_one_ror)
```

```
  if (n == 0) return(list())
```

```
  k <- ceiling(n / max_rows)
```

```
  if (k <= 1) {
```

```
    return(set_names(list(df_one_ror), ror_short))
```

```
  }
```

```
chunks <- split(df_one_ror, ceiling(seq_len(n) / max_rows))
```

```
nm <- sprintf("%s_%02d", ror_short, seq_along(chunks))
```

```
nm <- str_sub(nm, 1, 31)
set_names(chunks, nm)
}
```

```
sheets_by_ror_RAW <- works_by_ror_RAW %>%
  group_split(ror_short, .keep = TRUE) %>%
  map(\(df) {
    r <- df$ror_short[1]
    build_sheet_list(df, ror_short = r, max_rows = max_rows_per_sheet)
  }) %>%
  flatten()
```

```
names(sheets_by_ror_RAW) <- make.unique(names(sheets_by_ror_RAW), sep = "_")
```

```
write_csv(works_by_ror_RAW, file.path(base_dir, "openalex_works_by_ror_RAW.csv"))
write_csv(doi_unique, file.path(base_dir, "openalex_doi_list_unique.csv"))
```

```
out_xlsx <- file.path(base_dir, "openalex_dois_by_ror.xlsx")
```

```
write_xlsx(
  c(
    list(
      works_by_ror_RAW = works_by_ror_RAW,
      works_by_ror_dedup_work = works_by_ror_dedup_work,
```

```

works_by_ror_dedup_doi = works_by_ror_dedup_doi,
doi_unique           = doi_unique,
counts_by_ror       = counts_by_ror
),
sheets_by_ror_RAW
),
out_xlsx
)

cat("Saved:\n",
"- openalex_works_by_ror_RAW.csv\n",
"- openalex_doi_list_unique.csv\n",
"- openalex_dois_by_ror.xlsx\n",
"Note: Per-ROR sheets are built from RAW and split if >", max_rows_per_sheet, "rows.\n")

```

4. Overton search and recording coverage per ROR

Goal: Determine how many outputs indexed in Overton are found for each institution ROR using DOI-based searching, and record these results in the `counts_by_ror` sheet for comparison with OpenAlex DOI coverage.

Procedure / logic (as executed):

- DOIs were taken **per institution** from the per-ROR worksheets in `openalex_dois_by_ror.xlsx` (each worksheet corresponds to one ROR, with additional `<ROR>_01`, `<ROR>_02`, ... sheets where applicable).
- For each ROR, a DOI-based search was run in Overton using the DOI list extracted from that ROR's worksheet(s).

- The number of results returned by Overton for each ROR-level DOI search was recorded manually by adding a new column in `counts_by_ror` (e.g., `n_overton_found`) and filling it **for each ROR** with the corresponding Overton result count.
- After completing all ROR-level searches and recording their counts, the **global unique DOI list** (`doi_unique`) was used to run an **overall** Overton DOI-based query to obtain the total number of Overton-indexed outputs matched across all institutions combined (i.e., deduplicated across RORs).

Notes / interpretation:

- The per-ROR Overton counts (`n_overton_found`) reflect Overton coverage **by institution DOI set** and may include overlaps across institutions (the same DOI can appear under multiple RORs due to multi-affiliation).
- The global Overton count based on `doi_unique` represents the **overall deduplicated** Overton coverage across the full DOI corpus.
- Recording both levels enables:
 - institution-level comparison: `n_dois` (OpenAlex DOI count per ROR) vs `n_overton_found` (Overton matches per ROR), and
 - overall coverage reporting using the deduplicated DOI set (`doi_unique`).

5. Visualised coverage

Coverage was visualised as the share of OpenAlex-indexed works that were also indexed in Overton for each institution (coverage = $n_overton_found / n_dois$).

For each institution, we calculated Overton coverage as $n_overton_found / n_dois$ and additionally reported the inverse ratio (≈ 1 Overton-indexed paper per N OpenAlex papers, where $N = n_dois / n_overton_found$).

Code:

```
library(readxl)
library(dplyr)
library(stringr)
library(scales)
library(gt)

path <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data/ROR DOI OVERTON.xlsx"

tab <- read_excel(path) %>%
  transmute(
    institution = NAME_EN_CAPS,
    n_dois = as.numeric(str_replace_all(as.character(n_dois), "[^0-9]", "")),
    n_overton = as.numeric(str_replace_all(as.character(n_overton_found), "[^0-9]", ""))
  ) %>%
  filter(!is.na(n_dois), n_dois > 0) %>%
  mutate(
    share = n_overton / n_dois,
    one_in = ifelse(n_overton > 0, n_dois / n_overton, NA_real_),
    missing = n_dois - n_overton
  ) %>%
  arrange(desc(n_dois)) %>%
  slice_head(n = 20)

tab %>%
  gt(rowname_col = "institution") %>%
  tab_header(
    title = "Overton coverage by institution (Top 20 by OpenAlex volume)",
    subtitle = "Coverage = n_overton / n_dois; "1 in N" = one Overton-found paper per N
OpenAlex papers"
  ) %>%
  cols_label(
    n_dois = "OpenAlex (n_dois)",
    n_overton = "Overton found",
    missing = "Not found",
    share = "Coverage",
    one_in = "≈ 1 in N"
  ) %>%
  fmt_number(columns = c(n_dois, n_overton, missing), decimals = 0, use_seps = TRUE) %>%
  fmt_percent(columns = share, decimals = 1) %>%
```

```
fmt_number(columns = one_in, decimals = 1) %>%

data_color(
  columns = n_dois,
  palette = c("#F1F5F9", "#475569") # light -> dark (OpenAlex volume)
) %>%
data_color(
  columns = n_overton,
  palette = c("#ECFDF5", "#065F46") # light -> dark (Overton found)
) %>%
data_color(
  columns = share,
  palette = c("#EFF6FF", "#1D4ED8") # light -> dark (Coverage %)
) %>%

tab_style(
  style = cell_text(weight = "bold"),
  locations = cells_column_labels(everything())
) %>%
opt_row_stripping() %>%
opt_table_outline() %>%
tab_options(
  table.font.size = px(12),
  heading.title.font.size = px(16),
  heading.subtitle.font.size = px(12)
)
```

Visuals:

Overton coverage by institution (Top 32 by OpenAlex volume)						
Coverage = $n_{\text{overton_found}} / n_{\text{dois}}$; "1 in N" = one Overton-found paper per N OpenAlex papers						
	OpenAlex (n_dois)	Overton found	Coverage	≈ 1 in N	Not found	
UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB	72,357	3,474	4.8%	20.8	68,883	
RUĐER BOŠKOVIĆ INSTITUTE	19,649	694	3.5%	28.3	18,955	
UNIVERSITY OF SPLIT	16,002	909	5.7%	17.6	15,093	
UNIVERSITY OF RIJEKA	15,206	722	4.7%	21.1	14,484	
JOSIP JURAJ STROSSMAYER UNIVERSITY OF OSIJEK	12,953	471	3.6%	27.5	12,482	
INSTITUTE OF PHILOSOPHY	6,668	33	0.5%	202.1	6,635	
UNIVERSITY OF ZADAR	4,657	150	3.2%	31.0	4,507	
INSTITUTE FOR MEDICAL RESEARCH AND OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH	3,023	482	15.9%	6.3	2,541	
UNIVERSITY NORTH	2,177	95	4.4%	22.9	2,082	
JURAJ DOBRILA UNIVERSITY OF PULA	1,954	94	4.8%	20.8	1,860	
UNIVERSITY OF DUBROVNIK	1,915	122	6.4%	15.7	1,793	
INSTITUTE OF PHYSICS	1,772	1	0.1%	1,772.0	1,771	
CROATIAN VETERINARY INSTITUTE, ZAGREB	1,669	178	10.7%	9.4	1,491	
INSTITUTE OF OCEANOGRAPHY AND FISHERIES	1,405	319	22.7%	4.4	1,086	
INSTITUTE FOR TOURISM, ZAGREB	1,351	58	4.3%	23.3	1,293	
CROATIAN GEOLOGICAL SURVEY	1,048	50	4.8%	21.0	998	
AGRICULTURAL INSTITUTE OSIJEK	957	48	5.0%	19.9	909	
INSTITUTE FOR ANTROPOLOGICAL RESEARCH, ZAGREB	953	34	3.6%	28.0	919	
CROATIAN FOREST RESEARCH INSTITUTE	941	92	9.8%	10.2	849	
INSTITUTE FOR SOCIAL RESEARCH, ZAGREB	657	93	14.2%	7.1	564	
INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC FINANCE	579	79	13.6%	7.3	500	
INSTITUTE OF ARCHEOLOGY	563	8	1.4%	70.4	555	
INSTITUTE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES IVO PILAR	550	37	6.7%	14.9	513	
CROATIAN INSTITUTE OF HISTORY, ZAGREB	543	9	1.7%	60.3	534	
INSTITUTE FOR ADRIATIC CROPS	522	37	7.1%	14.1	485	
INSTITUTE OF ECONOMICS, ZAGREB	518	102	19.7%	5.1	416	
INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURE AND TOURISM	513	24	4.7%	21.4	489	
INSTITUTE FOR MIGRATION RESEARCH, ZAGREB	402	50	12.4%	8.0	352	
INSTITUTE OF ART HISTORY, ZAGREB	383	0	0.0%	NA	383	
INSTITUTE FOR THE CROATIAN LANGUAGE	375	1	0.3%	375.0	374	
INSTITUTE FOR DEVELOPMENT AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS	353	19	5.4%	18.6	334	
INSTITUTE OF ETHNOLOGY AND FOLKLORE RESEARCH, ZAGREB	346	8	2.3%	43.2	338	

6. Comparison CroRIS - OpenAlex

Code:

```
library(readr)
library(readxl)
library(dplyr)
library(stringr)
library(purrr)
library(tibble)
library(writexl)

base_dir <- "C:/Users/majah/Downloads/CroRIS_Overton_data"
folder_ror_exports <- file.path(base_dir, "overton export research articles from DOI from ROR")

croatia_old_csv <- file.path(base_dir, "6022 articles-metadata-2025-12-02.csv")

croatia_new_csv <- file.path(base_dir, "croRIS_matched_dois_for_Overton-2026-02-12.csv")

out_xlsx <- file.path(base_dir, "doi_match_CroatiaOld_vs_CroatiaNew_vs_ROR_exports.xlsx")

normalize_doi <- function(x) {
  x <- as.character(x)
  x <- str_trim(x)
  x <- str_replace_all(x, "^https?://(dx\\.)?doi\\.org/", "")
  x <- str_replace_all(x, "^doi\\s*:\\s*", "")
  x <- str_to_lower(x)
  x <- str_squish(x)
  x <- str_replace_all(x, "[\\.,;]+$", "")
  x[x == ""] <- NA_character_
  x
}

get_doi_col <- function(df) {
  nms <- names(df)
  idx <- which(tolower(nms) == "doi")
  if (length(idx) == 1) return(nms[idx])
  idx2 <- which(str_detect(tolower(nms), "doi"))
  if (length(idx2) >= 1) return(nms[idx2[1]])
  stop("No DOI column found. Available columns: ", paste(names(df), collapse = ", "))
}

read_any_table <- function(path) {
  ext <- tolower(tools::file_ext(path))
  if (ext == "csv") {
```

```

  read_csv(path, locale = locale(encoding = "UTF-8"), show_col_types = FALSE)
} else if (ext %in% c("xlsx", "xls")) {
  read_xlsx(path, sheet = 1)
} else {
  stop("Unsupported file type: ", path)
}
}

```

```

extract_dois <- function(df) {
  doi_col <- get_doi_col(df)
  df %>%
    transmute(doi = normalize_doi(.data[[doi_col]])) %>%
    filter(!is.na(doi)) %>%
    distinct(doi)
}

```

```

cro_old_df <- read_csv(croatia_old_csv, locale = locale(encoding = "UTF-8"), show_col_types = FALSE)
cro_new_df <- read_csv(croatia_new_csv, locale = locale(encoding = "UTF-8"), show_col_types = FALSE)

```

```

cro_old_tbl <- extract_dois(cro_old_df) %>% mutate(source = "croatia_old")
cro_new_tbl <- extract_dois(cro_new_df) %>% mutate(source = "croatia_new")

```

```

cro_old_set <- cro_old_tbl$doi
cro_new_set <- cro_new_tbl$doi

```

```

cat("Croatia OLD export unique DOIs:", length(cro_old_set), "\n")
cat("Croatia NEW export unique DOIs:", length(cro_new_set), "\n")

```

```

# DOI-evi koji su novi u NEW (nema ih u OLD)
dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old <- setdiff(cro_new_set, cro_old_set)

```

```

# (opcionalno) DOI-evi koji su bili u OLD ali ih nema u NEW
dois_old_only_vs_new <- setdiff(cro_old_set, cro_new_set)

```

```

# -----

```

```

# 2) Read ROR exports folder as ONE union set

```

```

# -----

```

```

files_ror <- list.files(folder_ror_exports, full.names = TRUE)
files_ror <- files_ror[grep("\\.(csv|xlsx|xls)$", tolower(files_ror))]

```

```

if (length(files_ror) == 0) stop("No CSV/XLSX files found in folder: ", folder_ror_exports)

```

```

cat("Files in ROR export folder:", length(files_ror), "\n")

ror_dois_tbl <- map_dfr(files_ror, function(p) {
  df <- read_any_table(p)
  extract_dois(df) %>% mutate(file = basename(p))
})

ror_set <- unique(ror_dois_tbl$doi)
cat("ROR exports (union across files) unique DOIs:", length(ror_set), "\n")

# -----
# 3) Original OLD Croatia vs ROR comparison (unchanged)
# -----
dois_both <- intersect(cro_old_set, ror_set)
dois_only_croatia <- setdiff(cro_old_set, ror_set)
dois_only_ror <- setdiff(ror_set, cro_old_set)
dois_union <- union(cro_old_set, ror_set)

# -----
# 4) NEW Croatia-specific comparisons requested
# -----

# A) DOI-evi koji su u NEW Croatia, ali nisu u OLD Croatia
tbl_new_croatia_only_vs_old <- tibble(doi = sort(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old))

# B) Od tih novih (NEW-only), koji su i u ROR setu
dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old_and_in_ror <- intersect(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old, ror_set)
tbl_new_croatia_only_vs_old_and_in_ror <- tibble(doi =
sort(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old_and_in_ror))

# (korisno) Od tih novih (NEW-only), koji NISU u ROR setu
dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old_not_in_ror <- setdiff(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old, ror_set)
tbl_new_croatia_only_vs_old_not_in_ror <- tibble(doi =
sort(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old_not_in_ror))

# (opcionalno) OLD-only vs NEW
tbl_old_only_vs_new <- tibble(doi = sort(dois_old_only_vs_new))

# -----
# 5) Overview counts (expanded)
# -----
overview_counts <- tibble(
  metric = c(
    "Unique DOIs in Croatia OLD export",

```

```

"Unique DOIs in Croatia NEW export",
"Croatia NEW-only vs OLD (DOIs in NEW but not in OLD)",
"Croatia OLD-only vs NEW (DOIs in OLD but not in NEW)",
"Unique DOIs in ROR exports (union of all files)",
"OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs in BOTH (intersection)",
"OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs only in Croatia OLD export",
"OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs only in ROR exports",
"OLD Croatia vs ROR: Unique DOIs when COMBINED (union)",
"Of Croatia NEW-only vs OLD: DOIs also present in ROR exports",
"Of Croatia NEW-only vs OLD: DOIs NOT present in ROR exports"
),
value = c(
  length(cro_old_set),
  length(cro_new_set),
  length(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old),
  length(dois_old_only_vs_new),
  length(ror_set),
  length(dois_both),
  length(dois_only_croatia),
  length(dois_only_ror),
  length(dois_union),
  length(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old_and_in_ror),
  length(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old_not_in_ror)
)
)%>%
mutate(
  pct_of_croatia_old = ifelse(
    metric %in% c("OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs in BOTH (intersection)",
      "OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs only in Croatia OLD export"),
    100 * value / max(1, length(cro_old_set)),
    NA_real_
  ),
  pct_of_ror = ifelse(
    metric %in% c("OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs in BOTH (intersection)",
      "OLD Croatia vs ROR: DOIs only in ROR exports"),
    100 * value / max(1, length(ror_set)),
    NA_real_
  ),
  pct_of_new_only = ifelse(
    metric %in% c("Of Croatia NEW-only vs OLD: DOIs also present in ROR exports",
      "Of Croatia NEW-only vs OLD: DOIs NOT present in ROR exports"),
    100 * value / max(1, length(dois_new_croatia_only_vs_old)),
    NA_real_
  )
)

```

```

)

# -----
# 6) Existing DOI lists for OLD Croatia vs ROR (unchanged)
# -----
tbl_both <- tibble(doi = sort(dois_both))
tbl_only_croatia <- tibble(doi = sort(dois_only_croatia))
tbl_only_ror <- tibble(doi = sort(dois_only_ror))
tbl_union <- tibble(doi = sort(dois_union))

file_contrib <- ror_dois_tbl %>%
  group_by(file) %>%
  summarise(unique_dois_in_file = n_distinct(doi), .groups = "drop") %>%
  arrange(desc(unique_dois_in_file))

# -----
# 7) Write Excel with new sheets
# -----
write_xlsx(
  list(
    # SHORT SHEET NAMES (<=31 chars)
    overview = overview_counts,
    file_contrib = file_contrib,

    # OLD Croatia vs ROR
    old_ror_both = tbl_both,
    old_only = tbl_only_croatia,
    ror_only = tbl_only_ror,
    old_ror_union = tbl_union,

    # NEW vs OLD + relation to ROR
    new_only_vs_old = tbl_new_croatia_only_vs_old,
    new_only_in_ror = tbl_new_croatia_only_vs_old_and_in_ror,
    new_only_not_ror = tbl_new_croatia_only_vs_old_not_in_ror,
    old_only_vs_new = tbl_old_only_vs_new
  ),
  out_xlsx
)

cat("Saved:\n- ", out_xlsx, "\n", sep = "")

```